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USED PERSON-MONTHS FOR THIS DELIVERABLE

No	Beneficiary	PM	No	Beneficiary	PM
1	NERSC	0.4	8	FORTH	
2	IOPAN	x	9	EurOcean	x
3	NPI	x	10	IMR	x
4	UiB	x	11	AWI	
5	NAXYS		12	KM	
6	Stinger		13	UBAH (AP)	x
7	Mundal				

x) indicates that the time used is less than 1 working day.

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

PU	Public, fully open	X
SEN	Sensitive limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	
Classified R-UE/EU-R	EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444	
Classified C-UE/EU-C	EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444	
Classified S-UE/EU-S	EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444	

DELIVERABLE TYPE		
R	Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)	
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs	
DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.	
DATA	Data sets, microdata, etc.	
DMP	Data management plan	X
ETHICS	Deliverables related to ethics issues.	
SECURITY:	Deliverables related to security issues	
OTHER:	Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.	

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is the first version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the High Arctic Ocean Observation System (HiAOOS) project. The HiAOOS project will develop, implement, and validate several ocean-observing technologies to improve data collection in the ice-covered Arctic Ocean. The technologies are based on a network of multipurpose moorings in the Nansen and Amundsen Basins. The HiAOOS network will provide point measurements of ocean and sea ice and active and passive acoustic data for several applications, including acoustic thermometry, geo-positioning of underwater floats, detection of marine mammals, geohazards and human-generated noise.

The primary target group for data and other resources are scientists and students, research infrastructures and technology providers working with ocean observing, analysis and modelling of ocean processes in the High-Arctic Ocean. Secondary target groups include promoters of observing systems for the Polar regions and various stakeholders who need more knowledge about the Arctic and Antarctica. Both target groups include users and stakeholders directly involved with HiAOOS and external actors.

The DMP describes datasets and other resources that HiAOOS will reuse from other projects, as well as datasets and other resources that the project will generate. This includes an overview of metadata and data standards used, data licences applied, data infrastructures for long-term storage, and an estimate of size of the various categories of data. Furthermore, the DMP identifies potential users of the datasets and resources outside the project.

The DMP follows the Horizon Europe template for data management. Thus, the document is organised as follows. Section 1 introduces the datasets that HiAOOS will reuse from other projects, and those that will be generated as part of HiAOOS. Section 2 describes the strategy for ensuring that the datasets generated by HiAOOS will follow the FAIR principles for data management. Section 3 describes other resources that HiAOOS will reuse or generate, such as software, training material and multimedia objects. Relevant aspects of FAIR for these resources are described. Section 4 outlines the procedures for data management in HiAOOS, including responsibility for different tasks in the data and resource delivery chain. The next two sections address two key aspects of data management: data security and ethics. The final section identifies other aspects of data management relevant to HiAOOS.

This first version of the DMP presents the plan for data management within HiAOOS six months into the project. Therefore, both the categories of data products and other resources, as well as the extent of and concrete activities needed to fulfil the obligations of FAIR, cannot be described in full detail. The DMP is a living document and will be updated as needed during the project to consider new data products and resources available from other projects as well as data products and resources generated through HiAOOS activities.

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1. Data Summary

This document describes the data reused from other projects and initiatives, as well as data that will be generated within the HiAOOS project (<https://hiaaos.eu/>). These data will be used to develop and test methods and tools for application areas such as oceanography, acoustic thermometry, geo-positioning of underwater floats, detection of marine mammals, ice processes, geohazards and human-generated sounds. Selected data will be used in project training events and made available as part of the training material. All data and other digital resources such as tools developed in the project are accompanied by a license defining the ownership and rules for sharing, use and citation. HiAOOS will follow the FAIR data principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016), with data and other digital resources “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”.

The primary target group for data and other resources are scientists and students, research infrastructures and technology providers working with ocean observing, analysis and modelling of ocean processes in the High-Arctic Ocean. Secondary target groups include promoters of observing systems for the Polar regions and various stakeholders who need more knowledge about the Arctic and Antarctica. Both target groups include users and stakeholders directly involved with HiAOOS and external actors.

Figure 1 illustrates the different steps of the data delivery chain from the observations downloaded from an in situ observing system to a data product is published in a sustained data repository. The actual implementation of each step will vary depending on which observing system produces the observations and what data product is generated. The sustained data repositories will provide a DOI for data products as well as access through standard protocols to data portals, stakeholder applications (including Blue Insight digital platform for generating new products) and European data infrastructures. Section 2 will present initial information for some of the observing systems to be used in HiAOOS. Later versions of the DMP will provide more information, as the observing systems are designed and the requirements from different target groups are refined. For data products, HiAOOS will use standard metadata conventions such as CF (Eaton et al., 2022) and ACDD (ESIP, 2020), and standard data formats such as NetCDF (Eaton et al., 2011), WAV (IBM and Microsoft, 1991) and miniSEED (SAGE, 2024).

Figure 1 Data delivery chain for in situ observations and products in HiAOOS.

Reuse of data products and other resources from other projects is an important contribution to the HiAOOS project. Using existing data will ensure that methods and tools for the targeted application areas can be developed early in the project. Thereby, software with test data will be ready in time for training events to engage the target groups of the project. Furthermore, existing software for the data delivery chain will be reused for processing the new data collected in the project. In addition, existing materials will complement the training material that will be developed in the HiAOOS project e.g., training material in data management and operation of observing systems in the Arctic.

1.1 Data reused from other projects and initiatives

HiAOOS will reuse data from earlier and ongoing projects and initiatives collecting, analysing, and modelling processes and phenomena in the High-Arctic Ocean. An initial list of data products that will be reused is given below. The list of reused datasets is expected to grow during the HiAOOS project, as other initiatives and projects generate data that are useful for method development and/or training, which will be included in later versions of the DMP.

Oceanographic, seismological, and acoustic data products from UNDER-ICE¹, CAATEX² and INTAROS³ projects will be reused for development of methods and tools, and sample data will be included in training materials. These data products are currently being prepared, and their size is therefore not estimated. Planned data formats include NetCDF for oceanographic data products, miniSEED for seismological data, and WAV for acoustic data products.

NERSC data products will be licensed as follows: Unpublished data from UNDER-ICE and CAATEX will be licensed for specific use in the HiAOOS project. Example data products from these projects will be made available for use in training through NMDC⁴ or Zenodo⁵ with a Creative Commons license, along with methods and tools developed in HiAOOS. Quality-controlled passive acoustic data products generated by NERSC from INTAROS moorings (not yet recovered) will be published in NMDC and Zenodo (test data for training), with a Creative Commons license.

IOPAN oceanographic data products from the AREX⁶ long-term program and INTAROS will be licensed with a Creative Commons license. IOPAN products from AREX and INTAROS will be published in the eCUDO ODIS⁷.

A-TWAIN⁸ oceanographic data products from IOPAN and NPI will be reused for development of methods and tools, and sample data will be included in training materials., with a Creative Commons license. Some of these products are already available through

¹ <https://under-ice.nersc.no>

² <https://caatex.nersc.no>

³ <http://www.intaros.eu/>

⁴ <https://nmdc.no/>

⁵ <https://zenodo.org/>

⁶ <https://old.iopan.pl/hydrodynamics/po/cruises.html>

⁷ <https://odis.ecudo.pl/>

⁸ <https://www.npolar.no/en/projects/a-twain/>

eCUDO ODIS and the Norwegian Polar Data Centre (NPDC⁹). New A-TWAIN data products from mooring recovered during the HiAOOS project will be published in the same repositories with a similar licence. These data products will be available in NetCDF format, with metadata in accordance with CF and ACDD conventions.

Selected Arctic PASSION¹⁰ and Nansen LEGACY¹¹ oceanographic and sea ice data products generated by NPI will be reused for development of methods and tools, and sample data will be included in training materials. These products will be published by the NPDC, with a Creative Commons license, and will be available in NetCDF format, with metadata in accordance with CF and ACDD conventions.

Seismological data collected by the Norwegian National Seismic Network (NNSN¹²) and UiB will be reused for development of methods and tools, and sample data will be included in training materials. These products will be published through the UiB-NORSAR EIDA¹³ node, with a Creative Commons license, and will be available in miniSEED format with standard metadata.

Oceanographic data products published in NMDC will be reused for development and training in HiAOOS. This includes, among others, Norwegian Argo data and mooring data from the Barents Sea Opening. These products are licensed with Creative Commons and made available in NetCDF format with metadata in accordance with CF and ACDD.

1.2 Data generated by the HiAOOS project

HiAOOS will collect data using different observing platforms, combining mature and proven technologies and new instrumentation developed within the project. The collected data are categorised according to the National Ecological Observatory Network (NEON¹⁴) levels (Table 1).

Table 1. Definition of data levels for in situ data are based on NEON definitions (e.g., Ludwigsen et al. 2018).

Level	Description based on NEON
Level 0 (L0)	Raw data are unprocessed measurements and observations from a single instrument, observation, or field sampling technique in native collection units, such as voltage.
Level 1 (L1)	Calibrated or quality-assured data are generally from a single instrument, observer, or field sampling area. These data are transformed into standard scientific units and are generally at native measurement resolution. Data quality control occurs, spatial and temporal coordinates are provided, and data can be temporally or spatially averaged (to reduce noise and increase accuracy)
Level 2 (L2)	Corrects and/or fills in any gaps in time in the data that an individual sensor collects
Level 3 (L3)	Connects gaps in space between sensors collecting the same type of data
Level 4 (L4)	Processing combinations of different categories of data, include in-situ and remote sensing data, external data sets, and models

⁹ <https://data.npolar.no/>

¹⁰ <https://arcticpassion.eu/>

¹¹ <https://arvenetternansen.com/>

¹² <https://nnsn.geo.uib.no/nnsn/#/>

¹³ <https://eida.geo.uib.no/webdc3/>

¹⁴ <https://www.neonscience.org/data-samples/data-management/data-processing>

Planned data include:

Nansen and Amundsen multipurpose Ocean Observing System (NAMO) data: NAMO is a network of moorings equipped with low frequency sources, hydrophones with high accuracy thermistors, upward looking sonars, sensors for measuring pressure, salinity, and temperature (CTD), and acoustic doppler current profilers. NAMO moorings will be deployed in late summer 2024 and recovered in late summer 2026. Processed and quality-controlled acoustic and oceanographic data products will be published in NMDC through the NERSC TDS¹⁵ and NPI's NPDC. The products will be in NetCDF format with CF and ACDD compliant metadata. Low frequency acoustic data will be available through the UiB-NORSAR EIDA node in miniSEED format. Documentation of field experiments and data processing will be made public (D2.6). Access to the raw data, and technology from third parties will be restricted according to regulations (see section 6 for further information).

Transformative mooring and ice buoy data: New instrumentation with low-power-consumption sensors for acoustic and oceanographic measurements will be developed and tested in the project. Moorings and drifting buoys with the new technologies will be deployed in summer 2025 and operated for a period of a few weeks. Selected data from the transformative mooring with new acoustic array technology will be retrieved by a Remotely Operated underwater Vehicle (ROV) operated from a surface vessel during the deployment period. Sample data products from the transformative mooring and the ice buoys will be used to test developed methods and tools in the project, and possibly in training events. Quality controlled data products will be published in Zenodo with documentation of field experiments and data processing performed (D2.8, D2.9). Access to the raw data and technology will be restricted to protect the IPR of the companies developing the new ocean observing technologies (see section 6 for further information).

Mooring with improved near-real-time data transmission: HiAOOS will develop and test a mooring with near-real time data transfer to the surface. This mooring will be deployed in late summer 2025 and recovered in late summer 2026. These data and full period datasets will be published in PANGAEA¹⁶ and eCUDO ODIS, after processing and quality control. Data will be available from these repositories in ASCII and NetCDF formats, respectively. Documentation of field experiment and data processing will be made public (D2.7).

Established repositories for marine data will be used to secure long-term storage of data, as indicated above. These e-infrastructures will provide a unique persistent identifier (e.g., a digital object identifier (DOI)) that can be used to acknowledge the project, data collectors and other actors in the data delivery chain. All HiAOOS data products will be registered in the iAOS Portal, providing a common entry point to the data generated in the project.

An estimate of the amount of data for different categories of data will be provided as HiAOOS starts to generate data products.

¹⁵ <https://thredds.nersc.no/>

¹⁶ <https://www.pangaea.de/>

2. FAIR data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

HiAOOS will use standard metadata conventions and standard data formats for all data products generated by the project. These standard data formats include:

Network Common Data Form (NetCDF): Used for oceanographic data products and for products derived from acoustic recordings (e.g., spectrogram, average sound speed and temperature). NetCDF files are “self-describing” with a header describing both the structure of the file and metadata for discovery and interoperability. The header can easily be customised for specific products and new metadata elements can be added to the files to support data discovery and interoperability. Metadata will be provided in accordance with the Climate and Forecast (CF) convention and the Attribute Convention for Data Discovery (ACDD).

Waveform Audio File Format (WAV): Used for acoustic recordings from ocean moorings and moving platforms (e.g., buoys). Audio data in a WAV file can be compressed allowing for compact representation of large amounts of observations. Standard WAV include metadata to specify the structure of the data (e.g., number of channels, sample rate) allowing software to open files correctly. Other metadata must be entered into a separate file.

miniSEED: Used for seismological data products. The miniSEED format is a simplified version of the Standard for the Exchange of Earthquake Data (SEED) standard. This means miniSEED files contains only waveform data and limited metadata. FDSN StationXML metadata is included in the data files.

All data products generated by the HiAOOS project will be findable through established repositories (see section 1) and the iAOS Portal (<https://portal-intaros.nerisc.no/>) developed in INTAROS. The iAOS portal is maintained by NERSC. Metadata for data products reused from other initiatives and projects will be harvested from the data repository hosting these products and ingested into the iAOS Portal. This will provide a common entry point for the data products generated and/or processed in HiAOOS.

2.2 Making data accessible

Open data products generated by HiAOOS will be stored in sustained data repositories that will ensure secure long-term storage of the data and provide a unique identifier (DOI). The chosen repositories for marine data are those used by the project partners on a regular basis. In addition, the cross-domain repository Zenodo will be used for the test data accompanying training materials. All repositories provide open access to published data, with some offering an optional embargo period for data that e.g., is used in scientific publications. Access to raw data will follow the principle of “as open as possible and closed as necessary” (see section 6 for further information).

Data products from the new observing technologies developed in HiAOOS will be published in open data repositories after quality control. Metadata for these products will be registered in the iAOS Portal. NERSC will maintain the iAOS Portal, while the data repository operators will maintain the metadata catalogues in their data system.

Metadata registered in the chosen data repositories and the iAOS Portal will remain available after the HiAOS project ends, for a period of at least 3 years. The data product owners are responsible for ensuring that the metadata is maintained for their products.

2.3 Making data interoperable

HiAOS will use the standard data formats identified above, i.e. NetCDF, WAV and miniSEED. Metadata for NetCDF and WAV files will be compliant with CF, ACDD, SeaDataNet and CMEMS. The metadata structure will be based on the profile developed in INTAROS (Hamre et al., 2021). Seismological data in miniSEED format will include FDSN StationXML metadata.

NERC (National Environment Research Council) vocabularies (<http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/>) will be used to specify among others, parameter names and units of the variables in the data products. ISO 19139 schemas will be used to document the roles of participants in the data delivery chain. GCMD (Global Change Master Directory) Science Keywords¹⁷ will be used to specify keywords for the data products stored in NetCDF and WAV files.

2.4 Increase data re-use

HiAOS scientists collecting data in the project will provide documentation of the processing and quality control conducted for their respective data products, including information of the instruments used (except for details of transformative technologies). HiAOS data managers are in charge of formatting and publishing data products in sustained repositories. They will document the steps of preparing data products in standard formats and making these available through one of the chosen data repositories. This documentation will be made available through public project deliverables.

In addition, selected data products will be demonstrated to RIs and other stakeholders through the Blue Insight digital platform. This will showcase quality-controlled data products (level L1-L4), as well as methods and tools developed to generate higher level data products (levels L2-L4) aggregating and integrating HiAOS data products with data products from external sources. Blue Insight will obtain HiAOS data products through the data services of the chosen data repositories or by partner ingestion of data files from their own data servers. This digital platform will further ingest data from external sources for use together with HiAOS data products, methods, and tools. Having all these resources available in one system with data integration, access, processing, analysis, and visualisation, is expected to contribute to increased reuse of HiAOS data products for the targeted stakeholder groups.

Open data products will be licensed under a Creative Commons license. Data with restricted access will be issued with specific conditions for use of these data products. Such conditions will have to be agreed and signed by both data owner and data consumer before access to the product will be granted.

Other resources generated by HiAOS, such as videos, webinar, training materials, will also be issued with copyright and conditions for use. The aim is to facilitate reuse of these resources under these conditions prohibiting misuse and ensuring proper credit to the

¹⁷ <https://gcmd.earthdata.nasa.gov/KeywordViewer/>

originators, the HiAOOS project, and the EC. The conditions will include acknowledgement of contributions from other projects or initiatives, in cases of joint creation of resources. Use and adaptation of material from other projects will be duly acknowledged. Consent for use of photos, statements and video material will be acquired before publication. Acknowledgement and statements of consent will be included in the resource and its description.

3. Other research outputs

In addition to data products, HiAOOS partners plan to reuse and generate other digital resources such as software, training materials, videos, and webinars. These resources will be managed according to relevant parts of the FAIR data management principles. Such resources generated by HiAOOS will be made available through suitable repositories and other online platforms. This includes Zenodo for training materials, documentation, slide shows and webinars, YouTube for videos and webinars, GitHub or GitLab for source code, documentation, and training exercises. Furthermore, a Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) is planned. This will be hosted in an online e-learning platform.

Figure 2 illustrates some categories of resources that are expected to be reused and generated in the project. Specific resources that are reused and generated will be included in later versions of the DMP. At present, two repositories for storing other digital resources have been created:

- HiAOOS YouTube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/@HIAOOSEU>
- HiAOOS Zenodo community: <https://zenodo.org/communities/hiaaos/>

Figure 2 Other digital resources that can be reused or generated in HiAOOS.

4. Allocation of resources

Work packages 2 (Observing systems and field work), 3 (Methods and tools) and 4 (Use cases and training) have allocated resources in their budgets for preparing and publishing data products and other assets from the project. The data products will be made available through the sustained data repositories listed in Section 1. This will ensure availability of the data products during and after the project ends. The owner of each data product is responsible for documenting, formatting, and publishing their data in line with the project's data management plan (i.e., this document).

Work packages 4 and 5 (Communication and dissemination) will generate other resources such as training materials, webinars, online courses, and have allocated resources for this in their respective budgets.

WP5 has the overall responsibility for following up data management in HiAOS and will work closely with the other work packages that generates data products and other resources. This will ensure the quality and interoperability of data products, documentation (methods and workflows) and tools from the project, to be compliant with FAIR and support Open Science.

5. Data security

Open data products from HiAOS will be stored in sustained data repositories providing long term preservation and unique identifiers (DOIs) for citation. This will ensure that the data products are safely stored, curated and accessible during and after the project. Other open resources such as source code, test data, documentation, webinars, videos, and online courses will be secured in long term repositories such as identified in Section 3. This will ensure that the resources are maintained and accessible also after the HiAOS project ends. Metadata for open data products will be registered in the iAOS Portal.

Restricted data products such as raw acoustic data and raw data (level L0) from new observing technologies developed in HiAOS, will be secured in the partners' own infrastructures. This will ensure that the respective partner can protect their IPR and exploit their data within HiAOS and in new activities after the project ends (see section 6 for further information).

6. Ethical aspects

Data products (level L0-L4) and other resources generated by HiAOS will be managed according to the principle of “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”. This means that while HiAOS aims to openly share project results to the benefit of the society, including science and innovation, proper attention will be given to assessing and managing risks associated with potential misuse of these results. The risks associated with sharing data and other resources such as software and video material are closely linked to the category and content of the assets. Examples of assets that are candidates for potential misuse, include, among others, raw acoustic data, methods and tools employing AI technologies, videos and photos. HiAOS will put special attention to detect assets that have a potential for misuse.

Quality-controlled data products (L1-L4) will be published in a sustained open data repository to ensure long-term access. Raw data (L0) will be accessible by external parties upon written request with explanation of planned use according to national and international legislation e.g. for technology transfer and export control. Methods and tools, with associated documentation will be made available through Zenodo, as part of the training material from the project. Other training material, e.g. presentations, slides, exercises, will be made available through Zenodo.

The owners are responsible for declaring the result in the EC portal and to register if IPR and/or an embargo period is needed. The owner(s) are responsible for informing about the

potential for misuse or dual use e.g. in connection with machine learning/ AI. To ensure that HiAOOS results are as “open as possible” while at the same time reducing the risk of misuse of HiAOOS results (e.g. data, methods, tools, technology), procedures for exploitation will be implemented in WP6 (Coordination and management). The information will be reviewed by the Coordination Team and evaluated as part of the Ethics assessment. The review will be based on:

1. National and EU regulations for sharing of data, technology, and knowledge.
2. The HiAOOS Grant Agreement and HiAOOS Consortium Agreement.
3. Exploitation plans by the owner(s) for commercialisation and/or use in new projects.

A results owner can establish an agreement for joint exploitation with other partners or external parties. Agreements for sharing data, methods and tools, technology, or knowledge, must follow currently valid regulations or legislations (e.g., export control, sharing of knowledge), the HiAOOS grant agreement and consortium agreement, and any pre-existing agreements for exploitation of result(s) between the owner and other partners or external parties.

A partner can ask for an embargo period for new results by making a written request to the Coordinator, who will bring this forward to the Steering Committee (SC). If the SC does not approve the request for an embargo period, it will be resolved by the General Assembly, the highest decision-making body of the project. The request must include a justification for and the proposed length of the embargo period. The Coordinator, SC or General Assembly may ask the partner for additional information if needed.

Deliverable 5.1 Dissemination, exploitation, and communication plan addresses the procedures for handling personal data collected, e.g., in connection with registration for training events and newsletters. Personal data will be managed in accordance with GDPR as described in Deliverable D5.1. Furthermore, HiAOOS is assessed by an external Ethics Advisor during the project (WP7). This assessment will include topics such as potential misuse of results, routines, and procedures for Informed Consent for participants in HiAOOS dissemination, workshops, and training events, as well as for collection of personal data related to these activities.

7. Other issues

There are no other known issues at present.

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